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Research Article

THE IDENTIFICATION OF PHARMACOGNOSTIC ON THE EXTRACTION OF TRADITIONAL MEDICINE TO LANSAU OF MUNA ETHNIC OF SOUTHEAST SULAWESI PROVINCERuslin*¹, Henny Kasmawati¹, Sunandar Ihsan¹, Suryani¹, Nur Samsiar², Ardiyanti¹,
Zulfikar Tahir¹, Rahmat Darmawan¹, Elsa Alexander¹¹Fakultas Farmasi, Universitas Halu Oleo, Kendari Sulawesi Tenggara²Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Farmasi Makassar, Sulawesi Selatan**Abstract**

Lansau is a traditional medicine of Muna ethnic which comprised of 44 kinds of plants that was inherited and believed to have a restorative power in healing kinds of diseases that are consumed based on the trust and the philosophy values by Muna ethnic. This study aimed to find out the characteristic of pharmacognostic on traditional plants of lansau comprised of determination of the plants, the experiment on macroscopic (experiments on organoleptic, the observation to the characteristic of morphology) and the experiment on microscopic. The sample of this study was the plant of lansau consisted of: bhangkudu, kamena-mena, patirangka, soni, katapi, ghontoghe, Libbho, kaghai-ghai, lansale, daru, sirikaya, Sandana, Kataba-tabako, Sambiloto, Kambhadawa, Lakoora, Kerseni, Kusambi, Bhea, Dana, Radhawali, Katimboka, Wonta, Bandara, Bumalaka, Kulidawa, Gondu, Patiwala ngkadea, Komba-komba, Ladha, Tongkoea, Kaghuse-ghuse, Kumbou, Kaembu-embu, Rogili, Rogo, Kalamandinga, Kula, Ntanga-Ntanga, Padamalala, Kumis Kucing, Kabote-Bote, Tulasi dan Kasape. The sample was obtained in the District of Bata Laiworu the Regency of Muna Province of southeast Sulawesi. The determination result which was conducted in LIPI Bogor was gained data of name of plants from 44 of the medicine used in the extraction of lansau. Result of macroscopic experiment on color, odor, taste and size of the plants was different from the outcome of plant's microscopic which has the type of stomata, trichomes, and the concentrate of different vessel.

Keywords: Lansau, experiment on pharmacognostic, determination, macroscopic, microscopic.**Corresponding author:****Ruslin,**

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INTRODUCTION:**Background**

Indonesia is a multiethnic country which comprised of 300 group of ethnics [1], one of the ethnics that could be found in the province of Southeast Sulawesi is Muna ethnic. Each of the ethnic belongs their own way of benefiting the plants for the purpose of the medication. The structure of the extraction, composition, the process of making/processing was conducted traditionally based on the practical experience that was inherited by the previously generation [2].

Lansau is a traditional extract of medicine that is believed by muna ethnic from long time ago which comprised of 44 kinds of traditional plants which were taken based on the believe on religious and philosophical value of munaese [3-5]. The development in inventing of the updated medicine which resourced from the nature, should be supported by scientific data concerning to the kinds of the plants, the compound content, and its benefits through the experiment of its pharmacology and other experiments. This study aimed at helping to identify the materials of the plants. The study on pharmacognostic is one of the simple techniques that could help in identifying the standardization of the material of the plants which comprised of macroscopic, microscopic, and phytochemical screening [6-9].

The purpose of this study is to find out the characteristic of pharmacognostic on traditional medicine of lansau utilized by Muna ethnic comprising of the determination of the plants, the experiment of macroscopic (Experiment of

organoleptic, the observation on the characteristic of morphology) and the examination on microscopic.

METHOD OF STUDY:

Method used in this study was descriptive non experimental. Sample of the study employed was lansau consisted of: bhangkudu, kamena-mena, patirangka, soni, katapi, ghontoghe, Libbho, kaghai-ghai, lansale, daru, sirikaya, Sandana, Kataba-tabako, Sambiloto, Kambhadawa, Lakoora, Kerseni, Kusambi, Bhea, Dana, Radhawali, Katimboka, Wonta, Bandara, Bumalaka, Kulidawa, Gondu, Patiwala ngkadea, Komba-komba, Ladha, Tongkoea, Kaghuse-ghuse, Kumbou, Kaembu-embu, Rogili, Rogo, Kalamandinga, Kula, Ntanga-Ntanga, Padamalala, Kumis Kucing, Kabote-Bote, Tulasi dan Kasape. The sample was gained from the District of BataLaiworu the Regency of Muna the Province of Southeast Sulawesi. The process of determination was conducted in LIPI Bogor and the examination of pharmacognostic was conducted in the laboratory of the faculty of Pharmacy of Universitas Halu Oleo.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:*Result on the determination of the plants*

The determination of the plants was conducted in Herbarium Bogoriense, Lembaga Ilmu Pengetahuan Indonesia. The purpose of determination was to determine the validity of the sample utilized in this study. The following is the determination process that could be seen in table 1

Table : Result of Determination

No.	Traditional Name	Indonesian	Types	Class
1	Bhangkudu	Mengkudu	<i>Morinda Citrifolia</i> L.	Rubiaceae
2	Kamena-mena	Bungan Nona	<i>Clerodendrum</i> sp.	Lamiaceae
3	Patirangka	Pacar Air	<i>Impatiens balsamina</i> L.	Balasanaceae
4	Soni	Dengen	<i>Dillenia</i> cf. <i>celebica</i> Hoogland	Dilleniaceae
5	Katapi	Kecapi	<i>Sandoricum koetjape</i> (Burn.f.)	Meliaceae
6	Libbo	Awar-Awar	<i>Ficus septica</i> Burn.f	Moraceae
7	Ghontoghe	Timo	<i>Kleinhovia hospita</i> L.	Malvaceae
8	Daru	Belimbing Wuluh	<i>Averrhoa bilimbi</i> L.	Oxalidaceae
9	Lansale	Godong Puser	<i>Hyptis capitata</i> Jacq.	Lamiaceae
10	Kaghai-ghai	Meniran	<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> L.	Phyllanthaceae
11	Sirikaya	Srikaya	<i>Annona mucirata</i> L.	Annonaceae
12	Sandana	Angsana	<i>Pterocarpus indicus</i> Willd.	Leguminosae
13	Kataba-tabako	-	<i>Blumea</i> sp.	Compositae
14	Sambiloto	Sambiloto	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.) Nees.	Acanthaceae
15	Kambadhawa	Turi	<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i> (L.) Pers.	Leguminosae
16	Lakoora	Rumput Belulang	<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Poaceae
17	Kerseni	Kersen	<i>Muntingia calabura</i> L.	Elaeocarpaceae
18	Kusambi	Kesambi	<i>Schleichera oleosa</i> (Lour.) Merr.	Sapindaceae
19	Dana	Alang-alang	<i>Imperata cylindrica</i> (L.) Raeusch.	Poaceae

Continue.....

20	Bhea	Pinang	<i>Areca catechu</i> L.	Arecaceae
21	Radhawali	Brotowali	<i>Tinospora crispa</i> (L.) Hook.f. & Thomson	Menispermaceae
22	Katimboka	Paku Simbar Layangan	<i>Drynaria sparsisora</i> (Desv.) T. Moore	Polypodiaceae
23	Kulidawa	Jati	<i>Tectona grandis</i> L.f.	Lamiaceae
24	Kumbou	Nangka Hutan; Tarap	<i>Artocarpus teysmannii</i> Miq.	Moraceae
25	Patiwala Ngkadea	Tekelan	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	Lamiaceae
26	Ladha	Lengkuas	<i>Zingiber sp.</i>	Zingiberaceae
27	Kaghuse-guse	-	<i>Dalbergia stipulacea</i> Roxb	Leguminosae
28	Gondu	Berenuk; Maja	<i>Crescentia cujete</i> L.	Bignoniaceae
29	Komba-komba	Tembelean	<i>Chromolaena odorata</i> Miq.	Compositae
30	Bumalaka	Jambu Biji	<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	Myrtaceae
31	Wonta	-	<i>Scleria laevis</i> Retz	Cyperaceae
32	Sau Bandara	Ketepeng Cina	<i>Senna alata</i> Roxb.	Leguminosae
33	Tongkoea	Pulai	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> R.Br.	Apocynaceae
34	Kumis kucing	Kumis kucing	<i>Orthosiphon aristatus</i> Blume	Lamiaceae
35	Rogili	Sirih	<i>Piper betle</i> L.	Piperaceae
36	Padamalala	Kumis kucing	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> DC.	Poaceae
37	Ntanga-ntanga	Jarak	<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae
38	Kasape	-	<i>Flemingia strobilifera</i> L.	Leguminosae
39	Kalamandinga	Petai cina	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i> Lam	leguminaceae
40	Rogo	Buas-buas	<i>P. cardifolia</i>	verbenaceae
41	Tulasi	Selasih	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i> L.	Lamiaceae
42	Kabote-bote		<i>Ruellia tuberosa</i> L.	Achantaceae
43	Kaembu-embu	Sembung	<i>Blumea balsamifera</i> L.	Compositae
44	Kula	Sirih	<i>Artocarpus altilis</i>	Moraceae

The Examination of Pharmacognostic

The Examination of Macroscopic

a. The Examination of organoleptic

The examination of organoleptic was conducted could be seen in table 2.

Table 2: The Observation of Organoleptic properties.

No.	Plants	Parts of plants utilized	Colours	Odor	Taste
1.	Bhengkudu	Fruit	Dark Green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	concentrated
2	Kamena-mena	Leaves	Dark Green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	tasteless
3.	Patirangka	Leaves	Light Green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	tasteless
4.	Soni	leaves	Dark Green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	tasteless
5.	Katapi	leaves	Dark Green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	bitter
6.	Libbo	leaves	Dark Green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	bitter and tasteless
7.	Ghontoghe	leaves	Light Green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	tasteless
8.	Daru	leaves	Light Green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	tasteless
9.	Lansale	leaves	Light Green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	tasteless
10	Kaghai-ghai	leaves	Light Green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	tasteless
11	Sirikaya	leaves	Light Green	Distinctive Aroma	bitter
12	Sandana	leaves	Green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	Kelat and bitter
13	Kataba-tabako	leaves	purplish green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	bitter
14	Sambiloto	Herbs	green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	bitter
15	Kambadhawa	leaves	dark green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	bitter

Continue.....

16	Lakoora	Herbs	dark green	Odorless	tasteless
17	Kerseni	leaves	dark green	sharp aroma	bitter
18	Kusambi	leaves	green	Distinctive Aroma	tasteless
19	Dana	Rhizome	pale yellow	no distinctive odor	sweet
20	Bhea	seeds	brownish	Odorless	Kelat
21	Radhawali	stem	green gravishness	Odorless	bitter
22	Katimboka	stem	yellow brownish	Odorless	taste kealt
23	Komba-komba	leaves	dark green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	bitter
24	Bumalaka	leaves	light green	distinctive, odourless	bitter
25	Ladha	Rhizome	yellow reddish	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	hot
26	Patiwala Ngkadea	leaves	green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	bitter
27	Tongkoea	leaves	green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	bitter
28	Sau Bandara	leaves	green	distinctive, odourless	bitter
29	Kulidawa	Skin stem	dark green	Distinctive Aroma	tasteless
30	Kumbou	skin stem	dark green	Odorless	bitter
31	Kaghuse- ghuse	leaves	green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	bitter
32	Gondu	leaves	dark green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	bitter
33	Wonta	Herbs	green	Odorless	tasteless
34	Kumis kucing	leaves	dark green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	
35	Rogili	leaves	dark green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	somewhat hot
36	Padamalala	leaves	light green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	somewhat hot
37	Ntanga- ntanga	leaves	light green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	bitter
38	Kasape	leaves	light green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	bitter
39	Kalamandin ga	leaves	ligh green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	somewhat hot
40	Rogo	Leaves	light green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	somewhat hot
41	Tulasi	Leaves	light green	Distinctive Aroma and sharp	somewhat hot
42	Kabote-bote	Leaves	light green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	somewhat hot
43	Kaambu- embu	Leaves	light green	Distinctive Aroma and sharpless	tasteless
44	Kula	leaves	light green	distinctive aroma	bitter

b. The Observation on Morphology characteristics

Result on the observation on the characteristic of morphology could be seen in table 3.

Table 3: The Result on the Observation of Morphological characteristic

No.	Plants	The Outcomes from the Observation
1.	Bhangukudu	Fruit is oval or round, the color is green yellowish, flesh of fruit is thick, round seeds, and fruit is shiny and jagged.
2	Kamena-mena	Single leave, stem, long oval shaped, pointed tip, flat surface, diameter of the leaves is 6-12 cm and the width is 5-8 cm. the color is dark green, the protected leaves is white, length 2-3 cm.
3.	Patirangka	Single leave, big, long leave, jiggged edge, pointed tip, leaf bone pinnate. The bottom part forming a root rosette leaf width is 2 to 4 inch. The base of the leaf is sharp and pointed.
4.	Soni	Single leaf, long oval leaf, length 20-45 cm and width 8-19 cm, winged leaf stalk. the color of leaf is shiny green, winged, shiny color of the leaves, edge of the leaf is jiggged, parallel, round tip, the surface of the leaves is shiny.
5.	Katapi	Intermittent compound leaves, threaded up to 18 cm, pinnate leaves, oval, somewhat round tip, light green on top, dark green at the bottom.
6.	Libbo	Face to face leaves, threaded to 2,5-5 cm, oval leaves, narrow edge of leaves, dull tip of leaves, color of the leaves are shiny green, diameter of the leaves is 6-12cm. Colourful in both side of the leaves due to its pale color dominated the leaves.
7.	Ghontoghe	Single leaf, intermittent, round shape of leaf, yellow
8.	Daru	Intermittent leaves, odd with the number, short small leaves, oval, sharp round tip, flat edge, length 2-10 cm, width 1-3 cm, light green low surface.
9.	Lansale	Long oval leaves, jiggged sides, hairy long leaves in the surface.
10	Kaghai-ghai	intermittent compound leaves, light green colored, number of small leaves from 15-24, oval shaped, flat edge surface, round tip, dull tip, length to 1.5 cm, width to 7 mm.
11	Sirikaya	single leaf, interspaced ellipse long leaf, dull tip, sharp short tip, length to 6-17 cm, width 2.5-7.5 cm, flat surface, hairless, the surface of the leaves is shiny green
12	Sandana	fin intermittent leaves, interspace of odd number of leaves, oval round shaped, oval-shaped, length 4-12,5 cm and width 2-6,5 cm, the edge part of the leaf is sharp, flat surface. Edge part is round, flat surface. Light green colored in the surface, hairless. Major bone of the leaves is tightly hairy, short.
13	Kataba-tabako	Single and oval-shaped. Sharp long edge tip. Fine bone leaf, hard surface on the leaf. diameter of the leaf is 3-5 and width 9-12 cm.
14	Sambiloto	Single face to face leaves, lancet to likely lance. Sharp edge and flat surface of leaves. Fin bone of leaves, length of the elevate averages to 3-12 and the width is 1-3 cm. smooth surface on the leaves, thick.
15	Kambadhaw a	Intermittent double leaves (<i>bippinatus</i>), length of the stem of leaves 20-30 cm, and each of the stem consists of 20-40 pairs of small leaves. Lancet shaped of the leaves' tip is opened, round tip, fin bone of the leaves, flat surface on the leaves, hard surface.
16	Lakoora	The stem is round shaped, slippery, long straight stem, the size of the growth stem is 12-60 cm. dark green colored. single leaf with long straight line, round tip, open surface leaves, slippery surface and dark green colored, the blossom growth straightly or tend to growth at the side edge. Length of the seeds averages to 2.5-15 cm and white colored.
17	Kerseni	Single leaf with interspace, oval shaped. Smooth hair of surface, fin bone.
18	Kusambi	Intermittent leaf, even number leaves ad fin, waved leaf's side, hairless surface. Length of the leaf is 11-25 cm and the width is 2-6 cm.
19	Dana	Dana could be planted and growth straightly to the height of 0.5-1.5 m. Its rhizome coloured yellowish and bit pale long line, wild and unbreakable, the diameter of its rhizome is 1-4 mm, joint spaces, the part of the bone is appealed.
20	Bhea	Strong and hard texture triangle shaped short and round tip, length of the leaves 15 mm sampai 30 mm, the surface coloured brownish and greenish.
21	Radhawali	The length of the plant reached to 2-5 m, soft and wet stem. The surface of the stem is spotted and sided. layer surface lies in on the leaves
22	Katimboka	this is a type of strong and hard tree, the surface of the tree is hairy of reddish brown, the stem is hanging based on its characteristic
23	Komba-komba	Its leaf is ovale-shaped, the bottom part is wider, round tip, length of the leaf is 6-10 cm and the width is 3-6 cm. the edge of the leaves is jiggged, face to its peak, the position of the leaves is face to face. The bunch of the bossom lies in its branch (<i>terminal</i>)
24	Bumalaka	single leaf, short stem, length of the stem is 0,5-1 cm, the leaf is oval shaped and long, length of the leaves is 5-13 cm, width 3-6 cm, the side of the leaves tend to rolled upper position, upper surface is slippery, dark green colored, the bonnes is appealed around its bottom position, fine bonne.
25	Ladha	slim rhizome, branched tip, upside oval-shaped, in each of the branch there was found a

- line in the hole. the outer layer of the part is coloured brown yellowish, long, free fibre, short bench and fibered
- 26 Patiwala Ngkadea Kind of a clump plant height 0,5–1,5 m. the characteristic of the colour is brown, hard and spotted dark on its surface. The leaf is green oval-shaped and jiggged. The surface of the leaf is hard as it is hairy. Face to face leaf and the bones is fin, the stem is hairy and spined, the length is less than 2 m. the leaf is rough, aromatic and centimeter length, branches, square shaped. single leaf, oval-shaped, jiggged leaf, hairless, rough surface,
- 27 Tongkoea Waved and spotted skin of stem, thick to 3 mm. outer surface is rough, flat, peel able, fissures, break-coloured, and somewhat fibred.
- 28 Sau Bandara Intermitted leaf, dark and light green coloured of the leaves, oval-shaped, length 3-15 cm, width 2.5-9 cm, tip of the leaf is dull, peak of the leaf is angled, edge of the leaf is flat. Umber of the stem is 2 cm. bone of the branch is appealed at the bottom side of the surface.
- 29 Kulidawa single leaf, weary, dark-brown coloured, ovaled-shaped, length of the leaves is 20-40 cm, width 10-20 cm, sharp round tip, edge of the leaf is flat, bone of the leaf is jiggged, appealed at the surface, hairy,
- 30 Kumbou Kumbou is kind of a big tree plant sized 30-40 m, surface of the tree is crusted, oval-shaped, the stem is exuded, the tip of the peak and the leaf are dull, the surface of the leaf is soft and hairy, fin, tap root.
- 31 Kaghuse-ghuse dintermittent leaf, the colour of the leafs is light green, oval-shaped, length 1-3 cm, width 1-2 cm, tip of the leaf is round, peak of the leaf is round, flat, stem of the leaf 0,5 cm. Bone of the branch is appealed at the bottom of the surface.
- 32 Gondu the habitat of the plant is an annual tree with the height 10-15 m. the stem is wooded, round, branches, yellowish-white coloured, leaves organized intermitted and fin, each of the leaves is oval-shaped, the tip is sharp, length 10–15 cm, short stem, single bossom out of its branch, oval, the seeds is square and brown coloured..
- 33 Wonta Wonta is a monocotile plant, and its habitat is in a grassy area, its stem is wet, sharp and hollowed. The surface is rough and hairy. The growth is up straight (*erectus*). Single leaf with long sharp leaf, length 30 cm, wide 2-4 cm, edge of the leaves flat, dark green colored, greenish-yellow colored, the seeds are colored yellow and intermitted.
- 34 Kumis kucing Kinds of a shrubs plant, straightly growth, rooted, height 2 m. square stem, oval-shaped leaves, lancet, sharp, or dull at the tip part, size of the leaf is 1–10 cm wide 7,5 mm–1,5 cm, the veins are small, hair less, spotted on the surface.
- 35 Rogili Shrubs and vines, height 5-10 meter. The shape of the leaves is thin, like a heart, the stem is likely long, flat, and sharp. The peak of the leaves is hollowed, the bones are fine, the flies is thin, the surface of the leaf is green colored and slippery. Hairless at the bottom side of the bones and short hairy.
- 36 Padamalala Plant of is of green colored and stemmed. The leaves get along with the stem; the leaves are thick, long, and sharp. it has a shape like a ribbon, asthiri aromatic, when the leaves are pressed. rough and sharp tip of the leaves, arranged position, big leaves on the big stem, length of leaves 50-100 cm, wide 2 cm. flesh of the leaf is thin, smooth hairy at the bottom of the surface.
- 37 Ntanga-ntanga Shrubs plant, height 1-7 m, unarranged branch. Latex branch. single leaf, wavy, curved, the leaves fingered to 5-7main leaves, green colored, the color of the surface is pale compare to the upper surface length 6-15 cm length of the stem 4-15 cm
- 38 Kasape shrub plant, height 0,5-1 m, single leaf, face to face leaf, boned and fin, oval-shaped, round peak, light green coloured, flesh of the leaf is thin, smooth hairy on the surface, length of the leaf is 5-10 cm and wide 3-6 cm
- 39 Kalamandin ga small plant and classified in shrub plant, height to 2-10 m, rough stem, small size, cylindrical, tight hair, intermittent leaf, double fin, perfect, small leaf comprised of memiliki batang pohon keras dan berukuran tidak besar serta batang bulat silindris dan bagian ujung berambut rapat. Daun majemuk terurai dalam tangkai, menyirip genap ganda dua sempurna, anak daun kecil-kecil terdiri dai 5-20 pairs of leaves, lancet shaped, sharp, flat, length of the leaves is 6-21 mm and wide 2-5 mm
- 40 Rogo Medium kind of plant, height to 7 m. dark green colored, smooth hair, long shape, round and sharp tip, jiggged, thick flesh of the leaf, strong odor, width of the leaf around 3-6 cm and the length is 8 cm.
- 41 Tulasi Shrub plant, height to 60 cm to 300 cm. the colour of the leaf is brown-greenish, aromatic odor, somewhat hot, shape of the leaf is round, and oval, dull at the tip, fin bone, length of the leaf is 2,5 cm sampai 7,5 cm and the wide is 1 cm to 2,5 cm
- 42 Kabote-bote seasonal plant, height 0,4-0,9 m, single leaf, face to face, shaped round, sharp at the tip, length of the leaf is 6-18 cm wide 3-9 cm, the surface is slippery the color of the leaf is

- 43 Kaembu-embu dark green. thematic plant height to 0,4-0,9, straight stem, triangle, green color, single leaf, crossed at the front, round shape, round tip, round peak, jugged edge, length of the leaf is 6-18 cm, wider 3-9 cm, slippery, fine bone, the flesh of the leaf is thin, light green colored.
- 44 Kula height is 20 meter, the wood is smooth and rough fibred. The leaf is colored yellowish. The leaves are shaped wider and fingered, the tip of the leaf is sharp, length of the leaves are 20-30 cm, flat, wide face to the peak of the bosom of single plant.

The examination of microscopic

Table4: Result on the observation of microscopic

No.	Plants	parts of plants	Result of Observation		
			Stomata	Trichoma	vessel line
1.	Bhengkudu	fruit	testa, epikarp, and endokarp.		
2	Kamena-mena	leaf	Anomositic	Glandular	Radial
3.	Patirangka	leaf	Anomositic	Nonglandular	-
4.	Soni	leaf	Anisostic	Nonglandular	open-cholateral
5.	Katapi	leaf	Anomositic	Nonglandular	-
6.	Libbo	leaf	Parasitic		open -cholateral
7.	Ghontoghe	leaf	-	Nonglandular	Bicolateral
8.	Daru	leaf	Anomostic	Nonglandular	consentris amphikibril
9.	Lansale	leaf	Parasitik	Nonglandular	consentris amphikibril
10	Kaghai-ghai	leaf	-	-	consentris amphivasa
11	Sirikaya	leaf	Anomositic	Nonglandular	open cholateral
12	Sandana	leaf	Parasitic	Glandular	vessel system
13	Kataba-tabako	leaf	Anomositic	Nonglandular	closed cel of leaf of <i>Hellebrous</i>
14	Sambiloto	Herbs	Bidiasitic	Nonglandular	open-cholateral
15	Kambadhawa	leaf	Anisositic	Glandular	Amphikribal
16	Lakoora	Herbas	Diasitic	Glandular	Cholateral
17	Kerseni	leaf	Parasitik	Nonglandular	Amphivasal
18	Kusambi	leaf	Anisositic	Nonglandular	closed-cholateral
19	Dana	Rhizome	-		open-cholateral
20	Bhea	seeds	Endosperm, mesokarp, endokarp, seeds of aleuron, canal of noktah		
21	Radhawali	Stem the vessel lies inside the layer/endoderm of scheleencim,			
22	Katimboka	stem			concentric amphikribal
23	Komba-komba	leaf	Anomositic	Nonglandular	open cholateral
24	Bumalaka	leaf	-	Nonglandular	Idioblas
25	Ladha	Rhizome			open-cholateral
26	Patiwala Ngkadea	leaf	Diasitic	thron trichoma	open-cholateral
27	Tongkoea	leaf			Bikolateral
28	Sau Bandara	leaf	Parasitic	Papilla	opebn-cholateral
29	Kulidawa	skin, stem			open-cholateral
30	Kumbou	skin, stem	Diasitic	Multiseluler	closed-cholateral
31	Kaghuse-ghuse	leaf	Aktinositic	Multiseluler	Radial
32	Gondu	leaf	Anomositic	Nonglandular	Radial
33	Wonta	Herbs	Parasitic		concentric amphikibril
34	Kumis kucing	leaf	Anomositic	Nonglandular	open=cholateral
35	Rogili	leaf	Anomositic	Glandular	open-cholateral

36	Padamalala	leaf	Anisositic		concentric amphikibral
37	Ntanga-ntanga	leaf	Parasitic	Nonglandular	consentris amphikibral
38	Kasape	leaf	Parasitic	Glandular	consentris amphikibral
39	Kalamandinga	leaf	Diasitic	Nonglandular	open-cholateral
40	Rogo	leaf	Anomositic	Nonglandular	concentric amphikibral
41	Tulasi	leaf	Diasitic	Nonglandular	
42	Kabote-bote	leaf	Diasitic	Nonglandular	concentric
43	Kaambu-embu	leaf	-	Nonglandular	open-cholateral
44	Kula	leaf	-	Nonglandular	open-cholateral

CONCLUSION:

The result of the identification of pharmacognistic and the determination of 44 kinds of lansau, it could be concluded that:

1. The special character of lansau lies from its number kinds of plants in one extraction
2. Plants utilized is known as the medical for the community of Indonesia
3. Most of the utilized from the plants are the leaves, and some parts of the stem and skin, rhizome and herbs.

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